

Secure Processing Environments for Open Science: Proposing Legal Foundations

Final Recommendations

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Abstract: Open science incentives exist in difficult tension with countervailing requirements to hold data secure, and to mitigate downstream disclosures of data. Federated data analysis, and data visitation, has been proposed as a possible solution that captures the benefits of both open and restricted disclosures. This paper assesses the alignment between E.U. and global data protection institutions, and federated analysis. We conclude that the structure of data protection insufficiently accounts for how federated analysis networks are implemented in practice, from both an organizational and technological standpoint. We propose changes to foundational data protection instruments to better align its functioning to enable clear legal compliance on the part of federated analysis networks, enabling their more rapid uptake.

Impact: Our aim is to strengthen understanding of access control among EOSC constituencies and RDA members, while also promoting legal awareness of key issues related to secure processing environments. We seek to support the development of legally robust approaches to federated data analysis and to effective data access control within data visitation solutions.

Contribution to United Nations SDGs: As outlined in the Legal Foundations, considering means for protecting privacy and enhancing access control in data visitation systems is a necessary step for establishing appropriate conditions for inclusive and responsible research and innovation. These legal foundations can ultimately be instrumental for enhancing the processes for visiting personal data held by different data holders in respect of individual fundamental rights for scientific purposes, in particular for data visitation systems' development. Therefore, the Guidance contributes to UN SDG 9 (Industry, Innovation and Infrastructure), 10 (Reduced Inequalities), 16 (Peace, Justice and Strong Institution) and 17 (Partnerships for the Goal).

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Part 1: The Institutions of Open Science

The open science movement attempts to reduce barriers to participation in scientific enterprise on the part of both researchers and the general public. Numerous distinct motivations prompt the transition toward open science. Examples include – reducing the costs of innovation through making the knowledge and infrastructure required to participate in research more accessible; making science more inclusive and representative in reducing barriers to participation; holding scientists and academic organizations accountable, by making the outputs of their research available to civil society for critique; and fostering equitable participation in research on the part of actors in both the Global North and Global South. Arguments to speed the shift toward open science are often premised upon economic, distributional, and democratic justifications.

Implementing open science practices is itself a longstanding objective of scientific research communities. It has become all the more important in the last decade, as data-driven research displaces bench-science as the central method used to derive knowledge about biology and health. Open science is crucial to performing data-driven research, because deriving generalizable knowledge from large-scale datasets requires these to be made available with little to no administrative burden. Open science is a complement to most research – but it is of utmost necessity to large-scale, data-centric research. The newfangled formal requirements that funding agencies direct to researchers, requiring them to deposit data in open-access repositories, reflect the growing relevance of open science. So too does its explicit recognition in the recommendations of bodies such as UNESCO and the OECD.

How to incentivize researchers to invest effort in making their research outputs available to third parties is itself an area of intense debate and evaluation. Mechanisms used to mandate open data sharing include: the data release requirements of academic journals; universities' metrics for deciding on career advancement; the internal norms of scientific communities; the policies and contractual requirements of funding agencies; and the data publication requirements that clinical trial regulators direct to companies conducting clinical trials. Large-scale, transnational research consortia are funded to produce population-representative research databases organized across multiple sites, jurisdictions, and even continents. Data repositories, both centralized and federated, coordinate data management, storage, and access oversight functions, to make data from multiple studies available to downstream users in an efficient manner.

World-round, researchers and regulators grapple with difficult legal questions that pertain to the sharing of human biological data. Open science imperatives exist in tension with countervailing data protection requirements. The former strive to reduce the transaction costs associated to data use as much as possible, and create a global commons of scientific data. The latter require regulated actors to demonstrate compliance with jurisdiction-specific obligations to curtail the

downstream sharing of data about identifiable individuals, treating the processing and disclosure of such data as presumptively impermissible absent exceptional justification. International bodies dedicated to the generation and exchange of biomedical research data have described such requirements as chilling rote intercontinental data transfers, and delegitimizing well-established information flows essential to research.

Data visitation, or federated analysis methods, is the pooled analysis of data from across multiple organizations, without the data leaving the custodianship of its host organization. This generally involves the use of technical mechanisms to obtain the benefits of combinate analysis without requiring the transfer of personal data from one organization to another. It can also, less often, include ‘organizational’ forms of federation, wherein legal mechanisms such as contracts and policies are used to apportion respective compliance obligations among the participating organizations. Federated analysis has multiple advantages – from the standpoint of legal compliance, it is often thought to reduce the compliance burden that actors that submit queries to federated infrastructures, or those that make their data available for analysis through a federated infrastructure. It also decreases the appreciable risk of individual re-identification or data breach, in exposing personal data to smaller numbers of end-users. Last, it avoids incurring the astronomical data storage costs associated to the pooling together of data in central repositories for downstream use. Large numbers of research organizations have pivoted toward structuring their consortia as “federations” for reasons that are both pragmatic and strategic. Federation reduces the exposure of each organization to legal compliance risk, simplifies the otherwise complicated compliance activities needed to structure inter-organizational data flows, and is more economical relative to the cloud computing resources that are required.

Transitioning toward data visitation and federated analysis methods creates considerable organizational and technological advantages. However, there remains good reason to believe that further *legal* innovations will be required to best ascribe respective roles and responsibilities to actors engaged in federated data analysis. That is – to ascribe each actor the role that best motivates them to reduce the risks that their data processing activities create, whilst enabling them to demonstrate their compliance with their legal obligations. And this in a manner that incentivizes them to continue contributing data to research, and to utilize available data for their own research purposes.

Part 2 describes the E.U. legal framework that applies to the use of personal data and public-funded data, whether or not it constitutes personal data. E.U. law directs positive obligations to the creators and users of data to demonstrate that their data uses are compatible with substantive and procedural data protection requirements. It also creates positive legal obligations for public sector bodies to release both personal/regulated/sensitive data, and non-sensitive data, for downstream use. These provisions find application to public-funded research data. The description of E.U. laws that govern the use of personal data and public-sector information (PSI) is used to support a critique of the usefulness of the existing legal framework for open science communities that use federated methods (i.e., data visitation) to share data. We chose to analyze the E.U. legal framework because it is being promoted as a model for other jurisdictions to

adopt. To date, numerous jurisdictions have adopted data protection legislation modeled upon that of the E.U., and a subset thereof have started to mirror the PSI regimes that the E.U. directs to sensitive data (e.g., the Canadian province of Quebec). Because the E.U. model is a prevailing model that is attracting significant support and critique at the global scale – it is worthwhile to understand how its continued proliferation would affect the use of data visitation in furtherance of open science ends.

Part 2: The E.U. Legal Framework

The E.U. is implementing a transformative body of new legislation that elaborates how information can, or in some circumstances must, be processed or shared. Regulators are being created to interpret and to enforce such laws (e.g., GDPR supervisory authorities),¹ and supranational regulatory bodies devised to issue non-binding interpretive guidance (e.g., the European Data Protection Board, the European Data Protection Supervisor, and the European Data Innovation Board).² Novel legal statuses are accorded to private actors, granting them privileges, and subjecting them to correlative obligations.

Altogether, E.U. information policy endeavors to develop coherent legal boundaries to the use of information, that increases the benefits of such data use and mitigates the associated harms. It aims to balance private interests in data use against countervailing values, or against the directly competing interests of other individuals or organizations. The agenda is composed of a great number of Directives and Regulations. Key pieces implemented are: The *Database Directive*,³ the *Open Data Directive*,⁴ the *General Data Protection Regulation*,⁵ and the *Data Governance Act*.⁶ Proposed additions include: the *Data Act*,⁷ the *European Health Data Space Regulation*,⁸ and the *Artificial Intelligence Regulation*.⁹

Supplementing this legislation is a body of E.U. constitutional law that has guided the interpretation of the foregoing laws on the part of the Court of Justice of the European Union (CJEU), the non-binding Recitals that accompany each Directive and Regulation, and help to

¹ Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 95/46/EC (General Data Protection Regulation) OJ L 119, 4.5.2016, p. 1–88 at art. 51.

² *Ibid* at art. 68. See also:

³ Directive 96/9/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 11 March 1996 on the legal protection of databases OJ L 77, 27.3.1996, p. 20–28.

⁴ Directive (EU) 2019/1024 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 20 June 2019 on open data and the re-use of public sector information (recast) OJ L 172, 26.6.2019, p. 56–83.

⁵ GDPR.

⁶ Regulation (EU) 2022/868 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 30 May 2022 on European data governance and amending Regulation (EU) 2018/1724 (Data Governance Act) OJ L 152, 3.6.2022, p. 1–44.

⁷ Proposal for a Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council on harmonised rules on fair access to and use of data (Data Act) COM/2022/68 final.

⁸ Proposal for a Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council on the European Health Data Space COM/2022/197 final.

⁹ Proposal for a Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council Laying Down Harmonised Rules on Artificial Intelligence (Artificial Intelligence Act) and Amending Certain Union Legislative Acts COM/2021/206 final.

guide their interpretation, and the interpretive guidance of the aforementioned supranational regulatory bodies (e.g., the EDPB).

Though each of these laws is discrete and independent in its content and in its application, these laws together create rules of use, administrative bodies, and procedural requirements that are directed to balancing competing interests in the use of data. Major pieces of legislation are discussed, one by one, in the following paragraphs.

The General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)

The *General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)*¹⁰ is the flagship E.U. law directed to granting data subjects in the E.U. rights to informational self-determination, data protection, and privacy. It replaces its predecessor law, the *Data Protection Directive (DPD)*.¹¹ The GDPR has achieved international fame and infamy because of the heightened penalties and order-making powers that it contemplates, relative to the DPD.¹² The substantive contents of the GDPR do not differ a great deal from those of the DPD, though select novelties have been integrated. These include an obligation to integrate data protection into product development at the outset (to perform data protection by design and by default),¹³ and changes to the rules on joint controllership that recognize a heightened potential for networks of collaborators to be held jointly and severally liable for breaches of the GDPR.¹⁴

Beyond altering the substance of the DPD, the GDPR also creates new structures that tailor the application of data protection legislation to specified economic sectors and categories of data processing activities. This is achieved through co-regulation. Co-regulation entails the delegation of responsibilities from legislatures or from formal State regulators to non-government bodies for the development, adjudication, or enforcement of regulations.¹⁵ The GDPR enables sector-specific bodies to develop Codes of Conduct that tailor its application to better reflect the realities of those economic sectors,¹⁶ and to delegate to privately appointed bodies of sectoral adjudicators the role of interpreting and applying such Codes.¹⁷

The core substantive elements of the GDPR are the following. The GDPR applies to entities that choose how personal data will be used (i.e., controllers) or that actualize the use of data at the instruction of controllers (i.e., processors). Controllers bear the lion's share of responsibilities for

¹⁰ GDPR.

¹¹ Directive 95/46/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 24 October 1995 on the protection of individuals with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data OJ L 281, 23.11.1995, p. 31–50.

¹² See: Golla, S. J. (2017). Is data protection law growing teeth: The current lack of sanctions in data protection law and administrative fines under the GDPR. *J. Intell. Prop. Info. Tech. & Elec. Com. L.*, 8, 70.

¹³ GDPR at art. 25.

¹⁴ GDPR at art. 82 (2).

¹⁵ See: Balleisen, E. J., & Eisner, M. (2009). The promise and pitfalls of co-regulation: How governments can draw on private governance for public purpose. *New perspectives on regulation*, 127, 133-134. See also: Marsden, C. T. (2011). *Internet co-regulation: European law, regulatory governance and legitimacy in cyberspace*. Cambridge University Press.

¹⁶ GDPR at art. 40.

¹⁷ GDPR at art. 41.

ensuring that data is processed in a manner that respects data protection legislation. This is sound public policy because controllers use data to their own ends, and make all meaningful choices about how data are to be used.¹⁸ Therefore, the bulk of the burden for GDPR compliance rests with them. The actor that creates the risk bears the costs of the externalities which it creates.¹⁹ Processors have more limited responsibilities, such as ensuring the appropriate implementation of data controllers' instructions, and maintaining records of their data processing activities.²⁰ It is also possible for multiple organisations, acting together, to be categorized as 'joint controllers' relative to common data processing activities, where these organizations share the functions and responsibilities associated to controllership, relative to data processing activities that are carried out together.²¹

Controllers bear the following principal responsibilities. It is their obligation to identify a legal justification, amongst an exhaustive list enumerated in the GDPR (and implementing Member State legislation), for the processing of data that relates to identifiable natural persons (i.e., personal data).²² A second, additional justification must be identified to enable the processing of so-called 'special category data' – data that relates to specific protected attributes of natural persons.²³ In transferring data outside of the European Economic Area (EEA), it is also necessary for controllers to select a data transfer mechanism that affords such data considerable data protection and privacy guarantees – despite those data no longer being situated in a jurisdiction in which the GDPR applies after the transfer concludes.²⁴

Beyond demonstrating their authority to process or to transfer data as a precondition to performing those activities, controllers also bear substantive legal obligations. Examples are: honoring the rights of data subjects, maintaining records of their data processing activities, implementing appropriate security safeguards, performing a Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA), and appointing a Data Protection Officer (DPO). In addition, the foundational principles that undergird data protection law must be respected.²⁵ These include: limiting data processing activities to the purpose that is established at the time of data collection (and other compatible

¹⁸ GDPR at art. 4 (7), art. 24.

¹⁹ See e.g.: O'Connell, J., & Robinette, C. J. (1999). The Role of Compensation in Personal Injury Tort Law: A Response to the Opposite Concerns of Gary Schwartz and Patrick Atiyah. *Conn. L. Rev.*, 32, 137.

²⁰ GDPR at art. 28.

²¹ *Ibid* at art. 26.

²² *Ibid* at art. 6.

²³ *Ibid* at art. 9.

²⁴ *Ibid* at arts. 44, 45, and 46. In addition to these articles, it is worthwhile to consult the following jurisprudence: Schrems I (Maximilian Schrems v Data Protection Commissioner Case C-362/14 ECLI:EU:C:2015:650) and Schrems II (Data Protection Commissioner v Facebook Ireland Limited and Maximilian Schrems Case C-311/18 ECLI:EU:C:2020:559). The associated EDPB guidance is also relevant: European Data Protection Board, Recommendations 01/2020 on measures that supplement transfer tools to ensure compliance with the EU level of protection of personal data (2021).

²⁵ GDPR at art. 5.

purposes);²⁶ restricting data collection to the minimum necessary;²⁷ ensuring that data is accurate;²⁸ and not retaining such data longer than is necessary to fulfill the stated purposes.²⁹

Organizations are required to respect these obligations relative to identifiable personal data, as stipulated above. Identifiable personal data is data that relates to an “identified or identifiable” natural person.³⁰ The assessment of whether or not data is identifiable is performed in considering the inherent features of the concerned data (i.e., the presence of direct or indirect identifiers), the context of its storage, and the methods of re-identification that the controller(s) – and potentially also select other third parties – might use to perform re-identification.³¹

The Open Data Directive

The *Open Data Directive* harmonizes the contents of access-to-information (ATI) legislation throughout the E.U.³² Though it does not dictate which information Member States must subject to public release through their national access-to-information regimes, it harmonises the rules applicable to such access-to-information regimes once Member States do decide to release information to the public.³³ In addition, it creates a positive right for third parties to re-use information once such information is made public (i.e., Member States can no longer authorize the public release of documents without also allowing third parties to re-use such public-facing documents).³⁴ The decision to release information to the public remains with the legislative and executive branches of national governments.³⁵

The *Open Data Directive* builds upon two predecessor Directives, namely, the first³⁶ and second³⁷ iterations of the *Public Sector Information Directive* (PSI Directive). This prior Directive was first adopted in 2003, and was amended in 2013. In 2019, it was recast as the *Open Data Directive*.³⁸ The successive changes made to the Directive across its three iterations are numerous. However, major trends in its evolution include the following patterns.

²⁶ GDPR at art. 5 (1) (b).

²⁷ GDPR at art. 5 (1) (c).

²⁸ GDPR at art. 5 (1) (d).

²⁹ GDPR at art. 5 (1) (e).

³⁰ GDPR at art. 4 (1), GDPR at Recital 26.

³¹ GDPR at art. 4 (1), GDPR at Recital 26. See: Finck, M., & Pallas, F. (2020). They who must not be identified—distinguishing personal from non-personal data under the GDPR. *International Data Privacy Law*, 10(1), 11-36. See also: C-582/14 Patrick Breyer v Bundesrepublik Deutschland ECLI:EU:C:2016:779.

³² Directive (EU) 2019/1024 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 20 June 2019 on open data and the re-use of public sector information (recast), OJ L 172, 26.6.2019, p. 56–83.

³³ Open Data Directive at art. 3 (1).

³⁴ This change was first introduced in the 2013 version of the PSI Directive, that amended the original 2003 iteration of the PSI Directive. See the 2013 provision here: Directive 2013/37/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 26 June 2013 amending Directive 2003/98/EC on the re-use of public sector OJ L 175, 27.6.2013, p. 1–8 (2013) at art. 3 (1). See the comparator 2003 provision here: Directive 2003/98/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 17 November 2003 on the re-use of public sector information at art. 3.

³⁵ Open Data Directive at arts. 1 (2) (d), 1 (2) (f), and 1 (2) (h).

³⁶ PSI Directive 2003.

³⁷ PSI Directive 2013.

³⁸ Open Data Directive.

(i) First, the categories of information (referred to as documents) to which the law finds application has increased across the successive iterations of the PSI Directive, as have the categories of organisations to which the law applies.³⁹

(ii) Second, the degree to which bodies that release public sector information can charge fees for providing access to affected documents or data has been steadily curtailed across the successive iterations of the PSI Directive.⁴⁰ Entities that prior iterations of the Directive permitted to charge a “reasonable return on investment”⁴¹ in providing access to document increasingly trend toward being restricted to charging the “marginal costs” of providing access thereto.⁴² Later iterations of the Directive more often require select categories of regulated bodies to provide access to documents without charge.⁴³ The cumulative effect of these changes is to iteratively reduce the right of public sector bodies (and other organizations to which the law applies) to charge fees for providing access to PSI.⁴⁴

(iii) Third, the strength of the obligation of governments to enable the re-use of PSI has increased through time. Its substantive provisions first found application to those documents that the legislatures and the executive branches of Member State governments chose to make public and to authorize the re-use of.⁴⁵ The 2013 iteration of the PSI Directive first extended the application of the substantive prongs of the Directive to all of the public sector information that governments release, even absent an active decision on their part to authorize its re-use. By extension, it also mandated that all public sector information released be made available for re-use.

The changes made to the PSI Directive have increasingly opened up affected documents and information for downstream re-use. The re-use rights have become broader, the categories of information or organisations concerned more sweeping, and the conditions or formalities associated to such re-use more permissive. This reflects a change in the strategy of the European Commission regarding its overall information policy: open data is increasingly valued as an input into downstream economic activities and open science is increasingly privileged as a strategy to increase research output.⁴⁶

³⁹ See e.g.: Open Data Directive at art. 1. PSI Directive 2013 at art. 1. PSI Directive 2003 at art. 1. The Open Data Directive introduces “research data” and the documents of select public undertakings to its scope of application, both omitted from the 2003 Directive and the 2013 Directive.

⁴⁰ See Open Data Directive at art. 6. See also: PSI Directive 2013 at art. 6 and PSI Directive 2003 at art. 6. The Open Data Directive – at one extreme – precludes costs from being charged, absent an exceptional justification drawn from. Conversely, the original 2003 iteration of the PSI Directive anticipated that the providers of data could charge the costs of making data available to third parties plus a “reasonable return on investment.” Situating itself at the median position between these two extremes, the 2013 iteration of the PSI Directive authorized regulated parties to charge the marginal costs associated to the reproduction and provision of data.

⁴¹ PSI Directive 2003 at art. 6.

⁴² PSI Directive 2013 at art. 6.

⁴³ Open Data Directive at art. 6.

⁴⁴ European Commission (2020). Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee, and the Committee of the Regions: A European Strategy for Data at pp. 7 to 8.

⁴⁵ PSI Directive 2003 at art. 1.

⁴⁶ See also: Burgelman, J. C., Pascu, C., Szkuta, K., Von Schomberg, R., Karalopoulos, A., Repanas, K., & Schoupe, M. (2019). Open science, open data, and open scholarship: European policies to make science fit for the twenty-first century. *Frontiers in Big Data*, 2, 43.

The Data Governance Act

The *Data Governance Act* responds to multiple distinct public policy demands. First, it creates a harmonized pan-E.U. ATI regime for sensitive or confidential categories of data that are excluded from the general E.U. ATI regime detailed in the *Open Data Directive*.⁴⁷ Second, it creates registration requirements and substantive legal requirements applicable to private bodies that intermediate between upstream data holders and downstream data users.

Its first part establishes a PSI regime comparable to that of the *Open Data Directive*, but directed to PSI that is subject to disclosure restrictions. Examples include identifiable personal data, and data that is commercially confidential or subject to IPRs.⁴⁸ The PSI regime in the *Data Governance Act* resembles the early iterations of the *PSI Directive*, in that it creates minimal conditions that are applicable only once national ATI regimes elect to render restricted-access datasets available to third parties for re-use.⁴⁹

Determining the full conditions of the data re-use regime is left to the legislative and executive branches of national governments, as is deciding which restricted-access datasets will be made available for consultation, and which amongst those will be eligible for re-use. Overall, the PSI regime in the *Data Governance Act* completes that in the *Open Data Directive*, applying to the residual categories of information that are excluded from the application of the *Open Data Directive*. In allowing Member States to define the scope of documents that are subject to this regime, the *Data Governance Act* intentionally accords more discretion to Member State governments to autonomously define the structure of their access-to-information regimes for restricted-access data, than it does for PSI that is intended for unrestricted public release.⁵⁰

Beyond guaranteeing applicants for data access equitable and transparent conditions of data access and re-use, public sector bodies are empowered – and sometimes required – to implement measures to ensure that data is accessed in a secure and confidential manner. This includes: enabling data access through secure processing environments (discretionary),⁵¹ assisting prospective data users in re-contacting affected data subjects to obtain their consent to data re-use (obligatory),⁵² ensuring that access to confidential information does not lead to the dissemination of outputs that contain confidential information (obligatory),⁵³ and restricting the right of data users to perform outbound transfers of data to third countries outside the E.U./E.E.A. (often obligatory).⁵⁴

The foregoing ATI regime is facilitated by specialized administrative bodies that the Member States appoint, referred to as “competent bodies.”⁵⁵ These competent bodies provide support and services to the public sector bodies that bear obligations to release data to the public. Such

⁴⁷ See: *Open Data Directive* at arts. 1 (2) (c), 1 (2) (d).

⁴⁸ *Data Governance Act* at art. 3 (1).

⁴⁹ Compare the *Data Governance Act* at art. 3 (3) to the *PSI Directive 2003* at art. 3.

⁵⁰ Compare the *Data Governance Act* at art. 3 (3) to the *Open Data Directive* at art. 3 (1).

⁵¹ *Data Governance Act* at art. 5 (4) (a).

⁵² *Data Governance Act* at art. 5 (6).

⁵³ *Data Governance Act* at art. 5 (8).

⁵⁴ *Data Governance Act* at arts. 5 (9), 5 (10), 5 (11), 5 (12), and 5 (13).

⁵⁵ *Data Governance Act* at art. 7.

services include the operation of secure processing environments, data anonymisation or de-identification solutions, and the provision of support in coordinating the re-contact of data subjects to obtain their consent to the use of their data for secondary purposes.⁵⁶

The *Data Governance Act* foresees that local public sector bodies will not develop highly specialized expertise in the operation of secure processing environments, in the anonymisation and de-identification of data, and in directing requests for information re-use to concerned individuals. In this respect, it endeavors to create bodies that will specialize in these functions and carry them out on behalf of multiple public sector bodies, that cannot each efficiently develop and support such specialized functions internally. Delegating this function is itself a prudent public policy choice, apt to reduce transaction costs across organizations and to enhance interoperability in the practices of multiple public sector bodies absent their prior and intentional coordination. In other words – it enables specialization through the delegated centralization of governance functions to one singular body, which also ensures the interoperable implementation thereof across multiple delegating organizations.

The remaining sections of the *Data Governance Act* create a regulatory regime that is applicable to data intermediation services (DIs),⁵⁷ data cooperatives (DCs),⁵⁸ and data altruism organizations (DAOs).⁵⁹ DIs and DCs are private bodies that intermediate between upstream providers of data (either data subjects or organizations that process data) and downstream re-users of such data. DAOs are non-profit bodies that act on behalf of data subjects that choose to make their data available for pro-social downstream re-use.⁶⁰

The purpose of these bodies (which are of a private, rather than public, character) is to intermediate across individuals or entities that provide data to downstream users, and those downstream users. In essence, those bodies act as “brokers” that establish the conditions of data exchange and provide ancillary services at scale. The motivations for ascribing an explicit legal role to such entities are not difficult to understand. It is transaction-cost intensive for individuals and organizations to negotiate downstream access to data on a one-to-one basis. However, prior to the enactment of the *Data Governance Act*, it was difficult to determine whether or not it was lawful for third parties to take on responsibilities for exercising the rights of data subjects or other organizations holding data (e.g., data controllers) on behalf thereof. Explicit recognition of a role for private actors in articulating and negotiating rights in data between organizations and/or individuals legitimates the emergence of such markets and promotes investment in their development.

The *Data Governance Act* directs select obligations to data sharing intermediaries (i.e., data intermediation services and data cooperatives), and data altruism organizations. Data intermediation services are required to register with competent bodies before operating.⁶¹ DIs and DCs are required to silo their activities in a legal entity separate from that which performs

⁵⁶ *Ibid.*

⁵⁷ *Data Governance Act* at arts. 10 to 15.

⁵⁸ *Data Governance Act* at art. 10 (c).

⁵⁹ *Data Governance Act* at arts. 18 to 25.

⁶⁰ *Data Governance Act* at arts. 18 to 25.

⁶¹ *Data Governance Act* at arts. 11 (1), and 11 (4).

their other activities;⁶² and to not use such data for their own purposes.⁶³ In addition, these entities bear numerous obligations, such as to ensure “fairness, transparency, and non-discrimination,”⁶⁴ to prevent the misuse of their platforms; to “act in the data subjects’ best interest”⁶⁵ when acting on their behalf. The general thrust of these obligations is to provide the services concerned in a manner that is secure, lawful, and that respects the interests of both upstream and downstream data recipients. Non-compliance can lead to suspension of one’s status as a data intermediation service⁶⁶ and to fines being levied.⁶⁷ The obligations of DAOs are similar, but their substantive legal duties are less onerous than those of DIs and DCs, and their potential penalties for non-compliance are limited to abolition in the case of long-term non-compliance (i.e., there is no prospect for financial penalties to be levied against them).⁶⁸

Overall, the *Data Governance Act* must be understood as furthering two objectives. First, filling the gaps in the *Open Data Directive*. The *Open Data Directive* creates strong legal obligations for public-sector organizations to share their data (including public-funded research data), where it does not fall into select identifiable, regulated, or otherwise sensitive categories. However – the *Open Data Directive* does not create an equivalent regime that requires public-sector organizations to share such data where it falls into the foregoing ‘regulated’ categories of data. Prior to the advent of the *Data Governance Act*, public sector organizations thus bore no formal obligation to share such data. And this despite its significant downstream value for business, research, and statistical activities. The *Data Governance Act* addresses this gap through the creation of a common E.U. regime that harmonizes certain aspects of Member State ATI legislation, as it relates to restricted-access PSI data that is sensitive or otherwise confidential. Second, it grants legal recognition to both public and private, for-profit and non-profit, bodies that intermediate between upstream data providers and downstream data users. These latter organizations fill a niche in pooling the transaction costs that both upstream data providers and downstream data users would otherwise bear in negotiating bespoke data access on a case-by-case basis.

The European Health Data Space Regulation (Proposal)

The proposed European Health Data Space (EHDS) Regulation creates the first E.U./E.E.A. legal regime that is dedicated to enabling the pan-European exchange of health-related data, to enable both patient access thereto and its harmonized and interoperable downstream use.⁶⁹ The EHDS Regulation coordinates downstream access to data through Health Data Access Bodies.⁷⁰ These are State-operated administrative bodies that can issue permits enabling data users to gain access to centrally-managed health data, through secure processing environments.⁷¹ The Regulation

⁶² Data Governance Act at art. 12 (a). See also art. 18 (d) for a similar requirement directed to DAOs, though the obligation to silo one’s data in a separate organisation is not *explicitly* required of DAOs.

⁶³ Data Governance Act at art. 12 (a). Similar obligations are directed to DAOs at art. 21 (2).

⁶⁴ Data Governance Act at art. 12 (f).

⁶⁵ Data Governance Act at art. 12 (m).

⁶⁶ Data Governance Act at art. 14 (4).

⁶⁷ Data Governance Act at art. 14 (4).

⁶⁸ Data Governance Act at art. 24 (5).

⁶⁹ EHDS Regulation (Proposal) at arts. 3, and 10.

⁷⁰ EHDS Regulation (Proposal) at art. 36 to art. 39.

⁷¹ EHDS Regulation (Proposal) at arts. 45, 46, and 47.

requires such users to ensure their compliance with both a number of substantive legal principles similar to those reflected in the GDPR,⁷² and to restrict their data processing activities to those within the concerned secure processing environment.⁷³

Part 3: European Information Policy in Context

Overall, E.U. information policy accords role-based responsibilities to numerous actors. The role and responsibilities of each are in general defined through operation of law. That is – the law considers an actor to hold that role where their actions match its definitions, without them being required to self-select into performing it.

Data Protection Compliance is Strategic

With this context in mind – the turn toward federation can be interpreted in part as a strategic response to the default application of rules. Regulated entities that might otherwise be subject to data protection laws structure their activities through federated analysis to preclude being characterized as GDPR ‘data controllers’ or other roles that face a significant compliance burden. This structure is a threat to the normative functioning of data protection law. Rather than acting in good faith to reduce the risks that their data processing activities create, actors in the E.U. are instead motivated to reduce their processing of regulated data altogether, to minimize their responsibilities for compliance.

Data protection enables generalist regulators to free-ride on the specialist knowledge of the targets of the regulation. This is achieved in requiring the targets of regulation to describe their high-risk data processing activities and to determine steps to be taken to reduce the associated risks. This approach is referred to as co-regulation. In the case of the GDPR, however, the targets of regulation are presented with two options. It is their choice either to engage in the resource-intensive process of defining risks and mitigation measures, or to opt out of processing regulated categories of data altogether. For private-sector actors with a profit motive, this incentive structure can encourage them to engage in best-efforts compliance. However, for those actors that do not have intrinsic incentives to maximize their data processing activities – such as research organizations that share data – the incentive structure of data protection law can motivate them to reduce their use of data altogether, to protect themselves from the financial and reputational risk of being held non-compliant. In other words – for those actors that derive a personal benefit from their data processing activities, choosing between processing regulated data and avoiding falling within the ambit of regulation promotes the efficient balancing of social benefits and risks. Those actors that do not benefit from engaging in data processing activities, conversely, will often reduce their data processing activities to a degree that is suboptimal,

⁷² EHDS Regulation (Proposal) at art. 44.

⁷³ EHDS Regulation (Proposal) at art. 50.

because these actors can internalize the benefit of reducing their compliance risk, but cannot internalize the benefit of engaging in additional data processing.

Data Protection Roles Create Challenges for Research Networks

The second major challenge is the networked character of scientific enterprise – and of open science in a more general manner. Open science networks – both considering upstream data production and downstream data re-use – are composed of actors that collaborate in data generation in a ‘networked’ manner.⁷⁴ ‘Networked’ here means that each collaborator in open science endeavor engages in deep specialization. There are good reasons for these acts of specialization. In addition to generating the habitual cost-savings from which market-participating firms providing specialized services at high volume benefit,⁷⁵ a second role is here served.

Scientific research organizations cultivate tacit knowledge within their boundaries – that is cost-intensive to share or reproduce and (evidently) cannot be transferred through market transactions.⁷⁶ In addition – these organizations collaborate with other organizations (assembling into multi-organization consortia) to compete with other such consortia for research funds that enable them to perform research.⁷⁷ Individuals are induced to join specific research organizations first to benefit from training opportunities (to learn tacit knowledge that cannot be gained otherwise),⁷⁸ to participate in research activities in the furtherance of their careers and reputations (e.g., publication, funding acquisition, and knowledge dissemination),⁷⁹ and to hold roles that relate to their specific research interests and research abilities. Organizations privilege the acquisition of human and material capital that is relevant to their area of research– decreasing their research costs – and increasing their appeal to other researchers in this domain area. Collaborations of this nature between domain-experts produce positive spillover effects in the form of ongoing informal knowledge exchange (itself costless).⁸⁰ This produces an iterative and self-reinforcing process of further specialization,⁸¹ as research organizations reduce their costs and increase their appeal to researchers through continued specialization and through inter-organizational collaborative participation in processes of grant-funded research.⁸²

⁷⁴ Langlois, R. N., & Garzarelli, G. (2014). Of hackers and hairdressers: Modularity and the organizational economics of open-source collaboration. In *Online Communities and Open Innovation* (pp. 11-29). Routledge. See also: Benkler, Y. (2016). Peer production and cooperation. *Handbook on the Economics of the Internet*, 91. Benkler, Y., Shaw, A., & Hill, B. M. (2015). Peer production: A form of collective intelligence. *Handbook of collective intelligence*, 175.

⁷⁵ *Ibid.*

⁷⁶ See e.g., Stiglitz, J. (1999). Public policy for a knowledge economy. Remarks at the Department for Trade and Industry and Center for Economic Policy Research, 27(3), 3-6 at pp. 4 to 6.

⁷⁷ See also, Stiglitz 1999 at pp. 16 to 17.

⁷⁸ Chugh, R. (2013). Workplace dimensions: Tacit knowledge sharing in universities. *Journal of Advanced Management Science*, 1(1), 24-28. See also: van Rensburg, G. H., Mayers, P., & Roets, L. (2016). Supervision of post-graduate students in higher education. *Trends in nursing*, 3(1).

⁷⁹ See e.g., Bloch, C., Graversen, E. K., & Pedersen, H. S. (2014). Competitive research grants and their impact on career performance. *Minerva*, 52, 77-96.

⁸⁰ Stiglitz 1999 at p. 10.

⁸¹ See e.g., Langlois, R. N., & Robertson, P. L. (1992). Networks and innovation in a modular system: Lessons from the microcomputer and stereo component industries. *Research policy*, 21(4), 297-313.

⁸² Cruz-Castro, L., Bleda, M., Derrick, G. E., Jonkers, K., Martinez, C., & Sanz-Menendez, L. (2011). Public Sector Research Funding. Policy Brief. Innovation Policy Platform.

This context guides us in our understanding of the ‘networked’ character of collaborative open science efforts. Consortia assemble into a network of participants in which each network participant holds a delimited and narrow role.⁸³ Each participant performs its assigned function within the broader network – and together the actions of each specialized node that operates within the larger network enables the functioning of the whole.⁸⁴ Organizations will therefore participate in a number of different ‘consortia,’ collaborating with other members of the consortium so as to better compete against other consortia.

The insight that is to be drawn from this is that legal responsibilities for the use of information on the part of biomedical research consortia cannot be defined at the level of the legal entity relative to its use of information *in general*. Each of the constituents in a network of information exchange exists in a state of epistemic opacity regarding the outcomes of its own information-processing activities, absent consideration of the role of those activities relative to the broader network.⁸⁵ Defining compliance obligations at the level of the individual organization (rather than at the level of the network) ignores the fact that network-level information is required to enable organization-level compliance. The rational behavior of such organizations is to limit their participation in information-exchange networks to reduce their prospect of non-compliance for faults attributable to the overall consortium.⁸⁶ Or, to engage in compliance theatre that satisfies formal compliance requirements – without engaging in the high-costs acquisition of the information that would be required to assess – and ensure – compliance at the level of the network.

The GDPR does itself recognize a limited legal role for networks of collaborators in their use of information – that which is ascribed to joint controllers. Joint controllers are networks of organizations that collaborate in using information for a common purpose.⁸⁷ These organizations are required to frame and to discharge their obligations as one.⁸⁸ This is intuitively appealing and appears to respond to our above critique. The liability rules associated to joint controllership, however, frustrate these potential benefits. Participants in a joint controllership arrangement are subject to joint and several liability. That is – each member of the arrangement can be held liable in full for the non-compliance of the other participants in such an arrangement (or for that of the *entire* arrangement).⁸⁹ This incentivizes organizations to actively avoid organizing their conduct in a manner that could be construed as joint controllership – so as to avoid the potential liability that is associated thereto – to the point that avoiding characterization as joint controllers is commonplace compliance guidance.⁹⁰

⁸³ See e.g., Langlois & Garzarelli 2014.

⁸⁴ *Ibid.*

⁸⁵ See e.g., Langlois & Garzarelli 2014 at pp. 11 to 17.

⁸⁶ The ALLEA, EASAC and FEAM joint initiative on resolving the barriers of transferring public sector data outside the EU/EEA (2021). International Sharing of Personal Health Data for Research. See also, providing further theoretical support for this position: Gourd, E. (2021). GDPR obstructs cancer research data sharing. *The Lancet Oncology*, 22(5), 592; Molnár-Gábor, F., & Korbelt, J. O. (2020). Genomic data sharing in Europe is stumbling— Could a code of conduct prevent its fall?. *EMBO molecular medicine*, 12(3), e11421.

⁸⁷ GDPR at art. 26.

⁸⁸ GDPR at art. 26.

⁸⁹ GDPR at art. 82 (4).

⁹⁰ See e.g., Bernier, A., Molnár-Gábor, F., Knoppers, B. M., Borry, P., Cesar, P. M., Devriendt, T., ... & Maxwell, L. (2023). Reconciling the biomedical data commons and the GDPR: three lessons from the EUCAN ELSI Collaboratory. *European Journal of Human Genetics*, 1-8.

Research organizations have economic incentives, interactional conventions, and knowledge-transmitting functions that incentivize them to self-organize into networks of an inter-organizational and transnational character. Grant-based funding structures reinforce these inherent incentives. Conversely, E.U. information policy requires organizations to assess their compliance obligations at the level of the individuated research organization – and imposes deterrent, punitive sanctions on organizations that form part of research networks that engage in non-compliant conduct, as assessed at the level of the research network.⁹¹ The structure of E.U. information policy imposes upon researchers a near-impossible task – on the one hand, to engage in the plentiful dissemination and reuse of data through transnational networks (often as a condition of E.U.-source funding). On the other hand, either to discharge their compliance responsibilities at the level of the individuated network node, or to bear legal responsibilities for the compliance of the entire network.

Data Protection Roles Delegitimate Pre-Existing Institutions

The third and final challenge that data protection law poses for open science networks is that its formalization risks de-legitimizing the existing institutions that research organizations use to allocate rights and interests in research data. At present, research organizations use well-established workflows to apportion upstream and downstream rights and obligations in research data. First, researchers collaborate with their ethics committees to define permissible uses of research data, including the intended downstream storage and sharing thereof. Second, research organizations define contracts, policies, and IP licenses to communicate the permissions in research data to its anticipated downstream users. Third, administrative bodies, including data access committees (DACs), Data Access Compliance Offices (DACOs), and the token-issuers that authorize researchers to access decentralized networks of registered-access data, assess the credentials of prospective data users. These institutions are a well-oiled machine, and enable researchers to ascribe governance safeguards to their research data in a rapid, predictable, and cost-efficient manner. Using these institutions requires researchers to obtain feedback upon their intended data governance practices from ethical, legal, and scientific decision-makers within their host institutions. They constitute an efficient mechanism for defining obligations relative to research data and ensuring that those obligations are translated to end-users of data in a manner that secures credible commitment therefrom.

Data protection law has positioned itself as a parallel institution to the traditional institutions of bioethics and research data governance. For example – data protection regulators have published guidance that requires compliance with its substantive elements to be demonstrated in addition to compliance with traditional bioethics requirements. This rather than treating successful engagement with bioethics institutions as demonstrating compliance with data protection requirements also. The consequences of non-compliance with formal data protection law are often more severe than non-compliance with the data governance and bioethics requirements that research institutions administer at the local level. Consequently, novel data protection institutions

⁹¹ GDPR at art. 82 (4).

risk displacing the well-established institutions of bioethics and data governance, especially where these conflict. This would generate heightened transaction costs for research organizations that place increasing reliance on emergent data protection institutions to define and enforce their obligations in using data. Because the institutions of data protection are external to research organizations (i.e., the regulators are external thereto), these will not adapt to address changes in research practice in a fluid manner. Further, because the institutions of data protection are generalist institutions, these will generate substantive requirements that are less adapted to the realities of research practice than are the institutions of bioethics and data governance that are internal thereto.

Part 4: New Legal Infrastructure for Secure Processing Environments

Our proposal is the following. Open science networks require a certification mechanism that is directed to the approval or disapproval of specified models of ‘network’ or ‘platform’ design, so as to confirm that these are compliant with applicable legislation – that is, a mechanism to approve specific instantiations of a ‘secure processing environment.’⁹²

This proposal distinguishes itself from the traditional paradigms of data protection legislation or of E.U. information regulation in the following manners. First – the target of regulation is *not* the individuated organisations participating in an information-exchange network – but rather the structure and the functioning of that network itself. Second – the anticipated compliance mechanism does not entail the full delegation of responsibilities for determining compliance programs to network participants, absent feedback from a regulator or delegate thereof. Third, this legislation would not displace pre-existing instruments of E.U. legislation nor create a new layer of general responsibilities applicable to users of information.

The proposed model is the following. Organisations engaged in the processing of information would be provided with the right to define specified categories of data, processing operations, and technological infrastructure as a ‘processing environment’ or a ‘secure processing environment.’ Such an environment could include data and technological infrastructure outside of the E.U. or the E.E.A. Once a secure processing environment is defined – governance rules would be produced at the level of the processing environment. Such governance rules would include: the nature of the data to be hosted on the secure processing environment, the categories of actors that can access a secure processing environment, the purposes for which the data accessible through the secure processing environment can be used, and the legal and technological safeguards to be applied thereto. Bodies responsible for their application and administration would be defined. Upon the formulation of ‘governance rules’ that are applicable to a secure processing environment – these

⁹² EHDS Regulation (proposal) at art. 50. Data Governance Act at arts. 3 (b) and 3 (c). These laws require their targets to share data, and to do so using secure processing environments, in addition to ensuring compliance with their other pre-existing legal obligations (i.e., compliance with data protection legislation). Our proposal differs from this model in that it does not require the sharing of data through secure processing environments in addition to compliance with the general legal obligations that are directed to organisations that hold data. Instead, it anticipates that delegated committees could license networks of collaborators to share data through secure processing environments *instead* of demonstrating compliance with their other obligations (as this latter measure creates *equivalent* guarantees for protected individuals – data subjects – as do other substantive legal regimes that create obligations in the use of data, such as data protection legislation).

rules would be submitted to the appreciation and approval of designated independent assessors. Their confirmation of the 'governance rules' would authorize the functioning of the secure processing environment – and remove the stipulated acts of data processing from the jurisdiction of other categories of E.U. information regulators relative to the acts specified in the approved governance rules.